

The Dignity and God's Image in Every Human Being (Gen 1: 26-27): Challenges for Human Dignity in Africa

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Abstract: This article titled: "The Dignity and God's image in Every Human Being (Gen 1: 26-27): Challenges for Human Dignity in Africa" articulates that man/woman was created in the image of God. It is the quality attained in the course of creation. The image of God (*imago Dei*) in human being stands for the attributes of God in man which gives mankind a special dignity and status. The divine image in man points to the existential abilities to commune and fellowship with God, while dignity is the transferred unique and supreme moral worth of God, His very nature and resemblance as expressed in man/woman. Unfortunately, this privilege is taken for granted and abused in the contemporary African society. More often than not, we hear that the dignity of the human person were trampled upon via physical abuse, torture, disgrace, cruel punishment, inhuman treatment, assault, castigation, terror, harassment, murder, emotional trauma and humiliation of people. Instances abound all over Africa especially in Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Cameroun, Niger, etc., where Christians seeking for healing and restoration were forced to eat grass; mercilessly flogged to cast out demons and some had to swallow snake. Essentially, this paper argues and upholds the dignity and rights of human person and denounces what is essentially inhuman. Using descriptive and analytical methods, the paper underscores that the scholars, especially the biblical scholars, must courageously affirm that this dignity should be understood, maintained and presented in Africa, so that the dignity and God's image in every human being could be respected.

Keywords: Dignity, God, Image, Human Being, Creation.

Introduction

The Holy Bible gives a vivid illustration of what man/woman really represents. It confesses that God endowed man with glory and honour while man was only lower in comparison with God even to the slightest degree (Psalm 8:4-6). This constitutes God's image that brings human beings closer to the Supreme; and in the nature of existence provides a structure of absolute uniqueness within creation. This fundamental anthropological axiom of the divine similitude points to the fact that from the very beginning, man has been made *deiform*, an endowment with the ability to be like God. The divine image in man points to the existential abilities to commune and fellowship with God. This remains the major purpose of creation which man received at creation. It is quite unfortunate that this dignity has been abused, suppressed and denigrated through wanton murder, maim and disrespect of human beings, created in the image of God. More often than not, we hear that the dignity of the human person were trampled upon *via* physical abuse, torture, disgrace, cruel punishment, inhuman treatment, assault, castigation, terror, harassment, murder, emotional trauma and humiliation of people. There are examples all over Africa especially in Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Cameroun, Niger, etc., where Christians seeking for healing and restoration were forced to eat grass; mercilessly flogged to cast out demons; and some had to swallow snake. Essentially, this paper argues and upholds the dignity and rights of human person and denounces what is essentially inhuman. This is the crux of this

biblical exegesis of the Old Testament text, especially to draw the implications of Gen 1: 26-27. But let us understand the notion of creation.

The Notion of Creation

The word 'creation' has multifarious meanings. J. A. Baker confirms this when he observes that: "In ordinary parlance to "create" has affinities of meaning with a number of words, among which the chief are "conceive", "invent", "design", and "make" (Baker, 1970, p. 48). But the idea of creation belongs essentially to the language of religion. Creation is the bond we can see linking the world and God. Creation is the bond we can see linking the world and God. The meaning of creation follows from the meaning of God, and if the creation is mysterious, it is so because of the mystery of God.

The term creation expresses the way in which the world and everything pertaining to the world have their origin, ground and final goal in God. It can mean actively, the creative action of God, and passively, the totality of the world. It is an act by which God gives existence to all being outside of Himself. In the Bible, it is clear that God created everything that exists, the material and the spiritual as well, and He created it from nothing (*ex nihilo*). This is understood to mean that nothing outside of him existed before the creation of the universe.

However, it is good to note that our awareness of creation or the acts of creation is only a created awareness, an awareness within the creation or within the created world. It follows that every expression of that awareness will bear the marks of relativity, of limitation and of contingences.

As recorded in the Bible, the Jewish and Christian traditions maintain that God created the universe out of nothing in six days. He fashioned the first man, Adam from dust, and the first woman, Eve, from Adam's rib, and He gave them dominion over all living things. The Islamic story of the creation and Adam is His viceroy on earth. Some Jews and Christians have held that the Biblical accounts of a single act of creation is not to be taken literally. Instead, it symbolises the spiritual truth that all things come from one good God. Many Muslims hold a view that is essentially similar. Nonetheless, T. Mouiren, commenting on the importance and need of this biblical account of creation says: "The first verses of the Bible tell us the story of the creation. This is a reasonable point at which to begin any teaching, the beginning of the whole story, the "beginning" of time. There is nothing more logical than that. Yet these verses are relatively late" (1981, p. 30).

Accordingly, this word "creation" has many definitions from different authors but all of them are pointing at the same thing. We shall now proceed to consider some of these definitions. As we see from the *Dictionary of Philosophy*, creation can be said to be the action required both to produce the universe out of nothing and to be its indispensable sustaining cause (Sinha, 1992, p. 49). Similarly, Ott gives his own idea of creation when he says:

In philosophical and theological parlance, by creation is understood the production of a thing out of nothing (*productio rei ex nihilo*, i.e. non *ex aliquo*), and indeed, *ex nihilo sui et subiecti* (not *ex nihilo causae*, that is, before the act of creation, neither the things as such, nor any material substratum, from which it was produced, existed (1960, p. 79).

In his book, *Summa Theologica*, St. Thomas Aquinas clearly stated his own opinion when he says:

Creation signified actively means the divine action, which is God's essence, with a relation to the creature. But in God relation to the creature is not a real relation, but only a relation of reason; whereas the relation of the creature to God is real relation (1a, qu.45, art.3).

From the above definitions, we can generally conclude that creation establishes a relationship between God and man, between "Ens" and "entia". It involves production of something out of nothing. Therefore, creation can be said to be the production of the total being of the universe from nothingness, i.e. from no subject that exists anteriorly. This total production is not a necessary emanation, rather it is a free act accomplished by the divine fiat. It is not eternal but takes place in time.

It is pertinent to note that creation is based not only on divine revelation as we see in the Bible but also on all of the facts of true science are in harmony with each other. Some scientists have started to agree the fact that the origin of life can only be explained by postulating the action of a supernatural creator, or God. One form of the argument proceeds in part as follows:

A living thing possesses a series of attributes which sever it from the inorganic by a chasm across which there is no bridge. Hence, to account for life we are compelled to admit that...at some definite point in past time it was placed upon the planet by the operation of an extra-mundane cause....That cause must have been living, intelligent, personal. But this can only have been God (Joyce, 2003, p. 152).

Creation is not a change because to create is not to make something from something else. It is not properly the “gift of being” because every gift presupposes the presence of something to receive it, and nothingness can receive nothing. Creation is the production of being taken in its totality, by Him whose every essence is to be.

Admittedly, the term creation was expressed in various languages by terms taken from various realms. The Greek bible prefers *οἶκος* (*oikos*) which originally meant “to make habitable” and then “to found” (a colony, a city). The corresponding Latin word is “*condere*”, but the Latin church preferred “*creare*”, the strict meaning of which was taken over by the Romance languages and then in English, which the German languages used “*schopfung*” probably akin to English “shape”. None of these words were derived from a pre-Christian religious usage. Hebrew language however, had a word which was reserved for the divine action. Along with more general terms for making or forming, the word *יצר* was used from prophetic times on to designate God’s action on the world. This consistent usage is characteristic of the biblical doctrine of creation.

With reference to his relationship with God and the world, man, the creature who has historical (*geschichtlich*) existence is essentially a creature of God subject to earthly limitations (Gen 2:7). Accordingly, he is seen as a living personal whole. Hence, he is considered under several of his principal aspects as “flesh”, as “soul” or as “spirit” but not as a *compositum* with these as his parts. Theologically, this integral view of man is shown by the fact that the entire man as an indivisible whole (Kahner, 1993, p. 883). As a “whole person” in this sense (represented especially by the heart, as his definitive aspect, man does not “have” a soul and body, he “is” soul and body. This gives credence why the later OT when the hope of salvation is expressed in terms of hope of the resurrection of the body (Isa 26:19; Dan 12:2ff; 2 Macc 7:14).

The Essential Nature of the Human Person

By its nature, the human person has come to be regarded as the starting point of scientific investigation, thought pattern and beyond. However, to arrive at a consensus understanding of a human person is an uphill task. The starting point of human life has polarised people, sparking off many schools of thought. Some hold that the life of a human person begins at fertilization of the sperm cells and egg. Others say the human embryonic zygote is simply the product of fertilization which its developing states are just *totipotents* stem cells which have the potency to a mature organism. In other words, for them, the human person has not started at this point. According to Ernest Ludwig Winnacker, the president of German Research Community and a member of Germany’s National Ethics Council: “Life begins with the fusion of the eggs and sperm cells. However, sperm and egg cells themselves are also human life” (Ekennia, 2003, p. 15). He arrived at this position by criticizing the position of those who said that the human person does not begin at the fertilization; that it is only at a later stage. The human person is always in the process of actualising its potency. Whether it is after birth or while still as a foetus, human life has started since if such is terminated, the life ends and conversely. In this regard, Thomas Berg adduced: “The most elemental philosophical rigor assures us that being (*or the* what a something is) *precedes* operation (*or the* what a something does or is actually capable of doing). A duck may be in a coma, unable to walk, quack, or lay eggs, but it’s still a duck” (Berg, 2003, p. 13).

The Church teaches that the human being is created by God in His own image and likeness, differing from the animals in the possession of a spiritual intelligence and free will (see Gen 1:26-31). One thing is physically definite, the coming of the human being is through the fusion of sperm cells (male) and egg (female); the creation of the soul, however, is the direct action of God (see Gen 2:7; 2 Mac 7:22-23) and this calls each person to exist in relation to God Himself (see Psalm 22:10). Each person is unique; there are no two persons who have the same destiny even the identical twins. Hence, the Igbo of Nigeria would say: “*Otu nne na-amu, mana obughi otu Chi na-eke*” (literally translated as ‘Giving Birth comes through one mother, but each has his/her own personal god/destiny’). Each person is called to maturity in the pursuit of eternal life in God.

Implications of *Imago Dei* (Image of God) in Gen 1:26-27

Imago Dei is defined as the image of God. The biblical accounts related to it started with the story of creation in the book of Genesis 1: 26-27: “Then God said, Let us make mankind in our image, in our likeness, so that they may rule over the fish in the sea and the birds in the sky, over the livestock and all the wild animals and over all the creatures that move along the ground.” This assertion means that in the mind of God, every creature created by Him is created in the image of God and after His likeness. Pearcey expressed that “the Bible does not begin with the fall but with creation: our value and dignity are rooted in the fact that we are created in the image of God, with the high calling of being His representatives on earth” (87). Every creature made by God as mankind is meant to represent or be an ambassador of God on earth. This principle of the image of God denotes that humankind by the act of creation makes man the exact thing with God. This Genesis story affirms that dignity and worth of man and elevates all men – not just kings or nobles-to the highest status conceivable, short of complete divinization.

By describing human beings as created in the divine image, the biblical tradition intended to define humanity as God’s representative on Earth (Redekop, 200, p.114). *Imago Dei* in environmental sense means ‘stewardly’ compassion and dominion. It simply means kindly use in a spirit of respect. Beers, writing about his visit in Tuscany, says, “As the hand of God formed all from nothing, He has entrusted to the Hand of man to do something with it. This is the purpose of creation: the man develop what God created. This is what I see and admired in the Tuscan orchards, vine yards, olive groves, and the herds of cattle and oxen: they are planted and led by human hands. They have not lain fallow; human stewardship is evident in their development. Even the wild poppies spring up the midst of human order. Here we see man and nature in harmony as God intended” (1997, vol. 7, no. 2). This is the type of spirit that invites us not only to develop societies, but also to pursue sustainable eco-system that are socially justifiable. This in turn would foster an ecological spirituality where shalom (peace) and harmony would reign supreme. A kind of harmony that is to be felt both externally as well as internally.

This understanding can be practically expanded. Accordingly, Grundem listed those areas in which man is like God as in the areas of “intellectual ability, moral purity, spiritual nature, dominion over the earth, creativity, ability to make critical choices and immortality” (443). Accordingly, mankind, as the apex of creation, greater than any other creation that were created by God, manifest all the attributes of God. Man/woman has all the abilities to reason and think whether they are able or disable and this is a major component of the image of God in him/her.

We can therefore sum up that dignity and image of God in man in the bible are widely diverse and complex. But the common denominators include:

- i) The dignity and the image of God refer to man’s spiritual qualities. The qualities which resulted in man’s ability for self-consciousness and intellectualism (including understanding, rationality, decision making and responsibility), righteousness, holiness, love, immortality, vitality, and the nobility of reflecting the glory of God.
- ii) Idea of personality such as man’s dominion, which focuses on man’s ability to rule over other creatures.

- iii) Man's personhood emphasizing its uniqueness and personal entity.
- iv) Man's relationship which includes the association of the man to the woman, of man to God, of man to the world around him, and of man to himself.
- v) Man's son-ship, the concepts of rational and moral personality.
- vi) Man's whole being, which incorporates the views of man's corporeal form, relationships as men and women, relationships with God, dominion over the world, spiritual qualities, and intellectual capabilities (Wernow, 1996, p. 117-118).

Dialectics on Human Dignity

Like any other socio-scientific terminology, human dignity, as a concept, defies precise definition. This is because different people perceive reality differently. Werner Kahl made this point when he observed that the European concept of human dignity is individualist while West African notions of the concept are communitarian (2009, p 5). This Kahl attributes to the philosophy of the Enlightenment, which has shaped western epistemologies since the 18th century or so West Africans love to live in groups, so they organize their lives around different kinds of communities. In such communities, they define what it means to be human. To avoid contextual ambiguities, we shall, therefore, follow Werner Kahl's approach. He strives to explain human dignity from the biblical perspective. With this view clarified, we will then propose what may be regarded as a West African communitarian concept of human dignity.

Human dignity refers to human worth. Human dignity is God-given. While human dignity may be denied, violated, devalued or compromised, it cannot be taken away; it cannot be eroded because it is rooted in God's sovereignty. Theologically, human being is derived from the concept of *Imago Dei* (Image of God), the affirmation that humankind was made in the image of God (Gen 1: 26-27). As already noted, the concept underscores the worth of the human being, He made them in God's image and likeness, made them male and female, blessed them and named them humankind.

God imputed dignity to the human creature He created by making them in His likeness. He made them to be like God. Next, we are told God made them male and female, meaning, that gender diversity itself is God-given and ought to be a blessing and not a misfortune for human beings. God blessed them. That is, God bestowed favour upon the human creature He created. Finally, God named humankind. God identified humankind. In the New Testament (NT), we find the affirmation of human dignity exemplified in the ministry of Jesus Christ. We learn that everywhere Jesus went he honoured the worth of those he interacted with. The early church followed suit and continued their ministry after the pattern of Jesus Christ. Their interpretation of human dignity was promised of the implications of the Christ-Event for the human predicament (see Acts 2). Kahl points out how Paul, the apostle, demonstrates this truth in his witness to the Christian concept of salvation as he understood it. For Paul, sin desecrated the human being created in the image of God, but through the generous death and resurrection of Jesus, the Christ, those who have faith in God's son are recreated (2 Cor 6:17). Humanity becomes a new creature, therefore, when it believes in Jesus, the Christ as Lord and Saviour.

Challenges Facing Human Dignity in Africa

From the discourse above, it is obvious that challenges abound for human dignity in Africa, created in the image and likeness of God. By challenges we mean the difficulties, obstacles, negative effects and impacts on human being perpetuated by some pastors and pastoral agents. Human dignity in itself is not dehumanizing human beings. This is true because the reality and genuineness of human dignity cannot be questioned; however, some challenges drift away from the human dignity in Africa. By dignity we mean true worth, the quality that earns or deserves respect. But this is not always the case especially in the African context.

African human dignity with Christianity is a major challenge to contemporary African scholarship and leadership (secular and religious). More often than not, we hear that the dignity of the human person is trampled upon *via* physical abuse, torture, disgrace, cruel punishment, inhuman treatment, assault,

castigation, terror, harassment, murder, emotional trauma and humiliation of people. Instances abound all over Africa especially in Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Cameroun, Niger, etc., where Christians seeking for healing and restoration were forced to eat grass; mercilessly flogged to cast out demons; had to swallow snake; pepper grinded and mixed into the vagina of a woman accused of adultery; made to carry the pastor on a stretcher during preaching; private parts of women were desecrated in the name of anointing; extortion of money in the name of consultation fee for ministrations; using deep kiss to heal, sitting on the laps of women; women looking for the fruits of the womb having 'holy intercourse' with 'the man of God' in order to conceive, and so on.

In some isolated cases, the female folk who consult these "healers or powerful men/women of God" for healing are made to buy olive oil in the healer's shop. The healer himself applies the olive oil with reckless abandon sparing no part of the body and in some cases anointing naked women all over the body. In the most recent times, there was a video drama in a Warri Church, Nigeria that went viral in the internet, where a pastor uses the power of God on women to fight against husbands. A case in point was the day he ordered single ladies to pick any man they want to marry in the Church! Is this not an abuse of matrimonial consent, one of the essential elements of a valid celebration of marriage, enshrined in the authoritative teaching of the Church today? The list can go on *ad infinitum*. One is not far from the truth that disrespect for human dignity has become Africa's nightmare. For this very reason, fear of the unknown has been enthroned as challenges facing human dignity in Africa.

Admittedly, the human person is endowed with numerous and enormous qualities that should earn his/her respect more than other beings. These qualities require that human beings be treated in a way at par with them. The 1983 *Code of Canon Law* has provided the background to support the equality and dignity of all Christians (can 208) which would lead to the integral and fruitful human living. Respect for the dignity of human beings is non-negotiable.

The Psalmist wondered at the glory of God and the majesty with which He clothed human beings whereby he was made little less than a god. He was crowned with glory and beauty. He was made the Lord over the works of his hands and puts all things under his feet (Ps 8:5-6; 144:5). The writer of the letter to the Hebrews was equally puzzled by the great care and concern God lavishes on human beings (Heb 2:6-9). The challenge is that everyone needs to join in the crusade to launch into the deep (*duc in altum*) against all forms of discrimination, obliteration of harmful practices that debase those who attend healing ministries and crusades within worship. Any act channelled towards dehumanizing human beings or inflicting pain on them should be discouraged. This is because they amount to disrespecting the dignity of God's image in every person. The Genesis account stated clearly that, in the beginning, God created humankind both male and female in His image, that is, '*the image of God*' [*imago Dei*] (Gen 1:27). By virtue of this act of creation, God endowed man and woman with human dignity. In this respect,

..there is a growing awareness of the sublime dignity of the human person, who stands above all things and whose rights and duties are universal and inviolable. He ought therefore, to have ready access to all that is necessary for living a genuinely human life: for example, food, clothing, housing, the right to act according to the dictates of conscience and to safeguard his privacy, and rightful freedom even in matters of religion (*Gaudium et Spes* 1987: 26).

This portrays that human person is at the centre of creation with dignity. The human person is the apex of goodness, an enhancer and agent of goodness. The human person is the jewel of God's creation. Human life is both sacred and precious, thus deserving and demanding unalloyed attention and respect. We should never allow the craze for miracles, healing and search for security to becloud our views of ourselves and others, created wonderfully in the image and likeness of God. Consequently, we must respect life at all costs and by all means. The human person remains a 'theatre' of attention, the subject and sole beneficiary of a litany of inalienable rights and privileges (not excluding duties). Violation of these is considered '*contra*' human dignity and hence *contra Imago Dei*. There is no amount of energy, resources, (intellectual, economic and otherwise), expended in the noble objective of discovering, protecting and enhancing the lofty reality of the *Imago Dei* in the human person which should be considered sufficient enough.

The inhumanity of man to man emits some stinking odour. But why must humanity be in the constant and incessant violation of the principles of social justice. The inadequate openness to life, the gulf between speech and action, is alarming. Real though it may be sound chimerical as those who should spearhead crusade for justice, are themselves perpetrators of injustice. None aims at what is objective and for the common good. Everyone looks for a way to gyp others out. Consequently, all forms of cheating have been tagged with one name or the other under the smokescreen of smartness. There is a gradual diminishment of intimacy among men and women. The rich become richer, and the poor, poorer, and the force of the society joins with the strong to intimidate the weak; hence, destroying the equilibrium which nature has put between them. There ought to be a relatively equal standard of living among men/women because there is a common good in the establishment of society. In his Theory of Justice, J. Rawls pointedly notes that: "A society is a more or less self-sufficient association of persons who in their relations to one another recognises certain rules of contact as binding and who for the most part act in accordance with them" (1989, p. 20). Today, most leaders think that militarism is the only way to achieve and carry out their anti-masses policies. But how far have they succeeded? Obviously, it has always been counter-productive.

It is certainly correct to agree with prohibition on torture and inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment as one of the most important provisions in the Human Rights Act, Article 3. And it is an absolute right and under no situation or circumstance will it ever be justifiable to torture someone by any form of inhuman acts especially if the person is not a threat to the society. It is tragic that the reason for this unsavoury and inadmissible denigrating attitude during healing ministry meted to the human persons not only in Africa but the world over swings between ignorance and the obstinate refusal of some to live authentic human lives. Some people do not possess positive mind-set about the nature of human being; or at best they possess a truncated notion of humanity. For others, this knowledge has been overshadowed by the attraction of modern materialistic society. Following the dangerous trend tending towards their selfish interest, there is need for the stakeholders to recast their minds and educate the people in this regard.

Every case of disrespect to human dignity, whatever form it takes, is profoundly a challenge to justice, human rights and human life. To recognize this at the very outset is to embark on a meaningful journey that has real prospect of securing real human dignity between the clergy and faithful. Christianity, for instance, is a religion that explicitly prides itself on its commitment to justice in the world. One would hope that this commitment is clearly reflected not only in the principles and teachings of this religion, but also in its everyday life, institution, structures and patterns. All forms of violence and assault to human dignity are no more private offences. They have become a world-wide and criminal ones. If they happen, they must be reported to the police, who know how to restrain the perpetrator and prevent future violence. It is also highly advisable before then to report to other pastors and hierarchy of the Church. Such abuses, denial and violence are perpetuated by silence. When reported they can be monitored and checked (Kunjiyop 2008: 248).

Christian community should enable their people to change their mind-set, empower them to stand up to their rights and dignity, and to address the abuse of human dignity. It has to be admitted that Christian worship, by and large, has made significant effort to improve the status of the lay faithful. However reducing and eventually, eliminating disrespect to human dignity is feasible, but may not be easy; it requires the concerted efforts of all stakeholders who play significant role in the liturgical lives of the faithful. The Church therefore has the responsibility of championing an awareness campaign which will eradicate these attitudinal challenges. This awareness campaign should also promote the dignity of the human person and uphold the universal, inviolable and inalienable rights of the congregation. This campaign could be launched through homilies/sermons at the Eucharistic liturgy, special seminars and workshops, audio-visual programmes catechesis and through the diocesan magazine and newspaper. This paper suggests ways to realize the full, conscious, total and holistic healing. Both spiritual and physical healings would be on point if the intended results are channelled to respecting the dignity of God's image in every human person. Religion and culture teach values that respect human dignity and integral healing such as 'life is sacred', *Ndukaku* (life is more precious than riches/gold), etc. The watchword is that scholars, parents, community, individuals, pastors and the pastoral agents should

guide the steps of those oppressed and persecuted and let their human dignity be respected and their inalienable rights upheld.

Conclusion

The dignity of the human being is the bedrock of the Old Testament teaching on creation. Every individual is created in the image and likeness of God (Gen 1:26-27), which bestowed inherent worth and rights. This principle emphasizes that human life must be respected and protected from conception to death. This means knowing and respecting that the person is open to God, with his intelligence and will, he/she attains a freedom that sets him/her above all other creatures. Contrarily, the human person cannot be used as a means to achieve social ends, for example, by abusing workers or deceiving citizens. It stresses that each person is unique and unrepeatable, so it is not possible to suppress certain persons or their fundamental right to pursue social ends, no matter how urgent they may see.

Therefore, human dignity with Christianity should be accorded a priority status today more than ever. It is a priority to changing African religious reality, not in the sense of combatting the West but rather as a challenge for us in Africa to scripturally anchor our African religious matrix. It is affirmed that the dignity and God's image of every human being are biblically founded. Accordingly, scholars, theologians and theological institutes should design a course on "Religion/Theology and Human Dignity." In this way, they will be better informed to champion the path to respect for human life and the right to live. Human dignity is the source and foundation of every human right. This involves, *inter alia*, protection from any form of physical assault, protection against intellectual and mental assault as well as disrespect for human life. Human dignity is the fundamental value of the human person. Every human being has his/her dignity. Human dignity is therefore an attribute of every human person. Respect in the dignity of the human person is essential. Human person is a reflection of God's image and likeness (*Gaudium et Spes* 1987, 12). The submission of this paper is that respect for human dignity is very important for fruitful and integral human development. Enlightened empowerment and attitudinal change are mostly needed now to arrive at a better community where human dignity is respected and the inalienable right, is restored. And until we uphold the dignity and God's image in every human being, as recorded in Gen 1: 26-27, instead of predatory, derogatory, denial of human rights and dignity, Africa is doomed forever!!

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